

Virtual Private Network (VPN) over Multiprotocol Label Switching (MPLS) as a Secure Domain against DoS, DDoS & TCP Attacks

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Abstract— “Multiprotocol label Switching (MPLS) is a core networking technology that works between Layer-2 and Layer-3 of OSI reference model” [1]. This research aims to identify the key security issues involved in deployment of Virtual Private Networks using MPLS technology. Multiprotocol Label Switching is widely used and recognized tunneling technology that is used by many enterprise business organizations. The most common MPLS application today is Virtual Private Networks (VPNs). The use of VPNs over MPLS has increased over the past few years. Many large, medium and small enterprises are migrating to MPLS VPN networks due to its high speed bandwidth capability, providing highly available networks with high quality of service for mission critical business applications. However, at the same time, enterprises are much concerned about the security aspects of the MPLS VPN services provided by the service providers. The emphasis of this research is to find out which technology – MPLS or Frame Relay is more secure for a core network. This study is conducted to analyze the principal threats to a core network. The work can be done in a real environment configured using different networking devices. During communication across backbone (either MPLS or Frame Relay) we will generate different traffic -- DoS and DDoS. The reason for generating attacks to a core network is to analyze its impact on both technologies and response to the attacks.

Keywords— MPLS, RT, RD, VRF, LDP, TE

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-Protocol Label Switching is a technology which provides a mechanism for forwarding packets using labels. It was evolved in the late 1990s for fast packet forward mechanism for IP routers with the passage of time its potential have extended amazingly, like to assist service creation (VPNs), traffic engineering and QoS. The main reason for MPLS popularity is its flexible network-deployment nature as the term “Multiprotocol” indicates, the techniques can be used with different layers protocol and to improve the scalability of backbone networks to provide VPN solutions based on Layer 3 (Network Layer). MPLS help Internet Providers in order to have a high level network which provides better services to have a better and secure network. Communication in MPLS depends upon Labels which are attached between the Network Layer (Layer 3) header and the Data Link (Layer 2) in the case of Layer-2 technologies which are based on frames [2], and they are enclosed in the Virtual Path Identifier (VPI) and Virtual channel Identifier (VCI) fields in the situation where cell-based technologies like ATM are used. The reason for deployment of MPLS on the core network is to eliminate or avoid protocol dependencies on specific data link technology such as Frame Relay and Ethernet.

MPLS passes up the requirement of multiple layer-2 protocol for various types of traffic thus giving the unified structure. MPLS gives the benefits of unified network infrastructure, peer to peer MPLS VPN model and optimal traffic flow.

The primary duty of MPLS domain is to accept IP packets and forward as Label for rest of communication in the domain [3]. Packets enter to MPLS domain using the edge router of the network. Edge LSR is the router which accepts IP packets and assign label, while remove label and send IP packets out of the MPLS domain. The router accept IP packets and send as Label to MPLS domain are ingress router and remove label and send as IP packets out of MPLS domain is egress router. The ingress and egress depends on the flow of data. These packets are forwarded via Label Switch Router (LSR) that performs the function of routing which is solely based on labels. Label switch routers are also called provider edge router (PE) as it connects provider with customer and provider router (P) only performs the transitions. Labels disseminated among LERs and LSR use label distribution protocol (LDP). MPLS domain's packets are forwarded using Label Switched Path (LSP) which is unidirectional set of LSR facilitates the packets to reach to the specific destination. When an unlabeled packet enters into the MPLS tunnel through LER, the router initially find outs its Forwarding Equivalence Class (FEC) in order the packet to be in which then injects in the label in the new MPLS header and the packet is move to next hop. In case of labeled packet that enters MPLS domain the top most labels is examined and after determining contents of the label i.e. Swap, Push (Insert) and POP (remove) of label performed. In push operation the new label is pushed to the top, encapsulating the packet next layer of MPLS. These concept results in a hierarchal routing of packets in MPLS domain and more specifically in MPLS VPN, Whereas POP involves removing of outer most label that reveal the inner below label called dencapsulation. If the popped label was at the very end in the stack it leaves the MPLS tunnel via egress router.

II. RELATED WORK

2.1 Frame Relay

It is a WAN technology that works on the Layer-1 and layer-2 of the OSI reference model which means it is used as a backbone to provide services for the protocols of the network layer of the internet. It uses packet switching methodology that operates at high speed of 1.544 Mbps and allows bursty data. It has error and detection at the data link layer only. There is no flow and error control. Internationally, Frame Relay was approved by Telecommunications Standards Section (ITU-T)[4]. Data terminal equipment (DTE) and Data circuit-terminating equipment (DCE) are the connected Devices to the Frame Relay. DTEs are the terminating equipments and are located at the premises of customers like computer, routers and bridges. DCE are the carrier owned internetwork devices that is basically for the clocking and switching services. Permanent Virtual Connection (PVC) and Switched Virtual Connection (SVC) are two types of Frame Relay connections. [5]. PVCs are setup by network providers. It is dedicated point to point services. Switched virtual circuits are temporary connections established only at the time of data send between DTE devices across Frame Relay network. As data sends, it terminates the connection. The communication session across SVC fall in four steps of call setup then comes data transfer follows the idle stage and last the call termination. Permanent virtual circuits (PVCs) are permanently recognized

connections for regular & reliable data transfers. It operates on two state data transfer and idle. Frame Relay proposes an outstanding alternative to previous networks for connecting LANs to bridges and routers. Frame Relay is prevailing technology now a days but still it has some flaws as it is not suitable for sensitive data, there is a single point of failure in a host because of which all sites loose connectivity. It allows variable length frames which create delays in the network.

2.2 MPLS VPN

An MPLS VPN is designed to eradicate the weaknesses of link layer techniques like frame relay and ATM technologies with efficiency of routing. In simpler terms an MPLS VPN network is a combination of both network and data link layer. MPLS has gained a huge interest of service providers due to the high performance in scalability and potential low cost benefits. Enterprise customers expect the same level of security as they expect from ATM and frame relay which are based on layer two. Therefore providing a network that fulfils the requirements of business organizations with high performance backbone networks and high level of security is a tough challenge [7].

2.2.1 Overlay vs. Peer to peer VPN Model

In VPN networks, the two main functions performed by MPLS are packet forwarding and route distribution. MPLS uses LDP (Label Distribution Protocol) for packet forwarding and BGP (Border Gateway Protocol) for route distribution. Currently, VPNs are deployed on the basis of overlay model, to provide organizations the ability to connect multiple sites with the properties of a private network over a public network infrastructure. Each customer in a VPN is required to peer with a provider edge (PE) router in order to connect to another customer in a different VPN. The PE router is connected to backbone router with MPLS core. The provider controls the backbone network and shares the core among enterprise business customers. In other sense the networks are not private in reality but virtual private networks based on public network infrastructure [6].

2.2.2 Architectural Components of MPLS VPN

a) Virtual Routing & Forwarding (VRF)

One feature that brings uniqueness to the MPLS VPN label forwarding is the virtual routing and forwarding technique. This technology is implemented in provider edge routers. VRF are forwarding instances that are used with each separate VPN in a network. VRF enables routers to contain various routing table instances in the same router at a time [7]. By using VRF a router can have overlapping addresses for two VPNs since VRF are independent of each other [7]. The main purpose of VRF is to keep the privacy of each customer's routing information.

b) Route Distinguisher (RD)

Due to address limitation in IPv4 addressing companies cannot use public IP addresses over private virtual networks. To resolve the issue many organizations use private IP addresses for internal networks to avoid public addresses. The problem arises when any two or more companies using the same service provider services use overlapping addresses. In MPLS VPN each customer's routing and addressing should remain separate from every other customer in order to provide optimal routing. To ensure a smooth routing between different VPNs a 64-bit route distinguisher is added to the VPN. It is important to note that the route distinguisher was only introduced for IPv4 addresses or ASN (Autonomous System number) addresses. i.e. 64-bit of RD added with 32-bit IPv4 address [8].

c) Route Target (RT)

As the name indicates, route targets determine what routes should be imported into the virtual routing and forwarding table of provider edge router in order to provide communication between sites of two different companies. To make it simpler RTs have the function to decide what routes are visible to in which sites. A 64-bit value that is an extended community of BGP is used in extranet VPN. To understand the concept of extranet, let us take an example [7].

2.3 MPLS VPN Security

Due to increase in popularity as a framework for backbone network infrastructure for WAN design and implementation the increase in the security threats in the deployment of VPNs are raising a lot of questions among their subscribers. Though enterprise customers accept the high level of security from ATM and Frame relay [10] but customers are also concerned about the risks involved in deployment of provider provisioned VPN networks which are designed using these technology. IPSec is the most secure protocol but configurations are required on both customer and provider router [9], Whereas MPLS implementation is easier to deploy because configurations are made on the provider side of routers. Customer does not need to know about the technical side of the technology.. Due to the rapid increase of internet technologies and the growth in demand of customer needs worldwide the security of networks has become a critical issue. MPLS VPN is the technology which can be used in networks which can overcome the customer needs about security in their networks [10]. In MPLS VPN, every customer in a separate VPN has different security parameters [9]. Mostly, customers expect their data to be hidden from other VPN customers. Customers also expect their service providers to provide an MPLS VPN service that is available all the time without any outages [11].

2.4 Security of other WAN Technologies

Frame Relay a Layer-2 technology which consists of different nodes interconnected and provides virtual private connection. Frame Relay has less security threats than IP but less secure when we use IPSec is used to authenticate the packet but still address spoofing is possible [14] [15], IPSec can prevent a big threat about our network when addressing spoofing is used with denial-of-service: "Several high profile e-commerce sites were put out of business with the now infamous Distributed denial-of-service attack" [15]. The initial concern raised was about the structural design which could be receptive to DoS attacks from other VPNs or the web [14].

However, there are still vulnerability in Frame Relay like sniffing, passwords, war dialing, spoofing, hijacking [16]. **The main concern about Frame Relay VPN is security which becomes the reason of not using this technology anymore in the core networks. It is possible to secure or is secure MPLS based VPN while “it is not possible to make secure the infrastructure of Frame Relay or ATM”. [14]. This is the key research question to show that MPLS based VPN are more protected than Frame Relay to a large extent. The author of the paper although gave statement but there was no practical proof to support this statement. To ensure reliability of the above statement we will proof this statement by doing work in real environment.**

III. Design & Implementation

Implementation of any work gives us precise and better results to understand the underlying theory. Since a real environment would depict a realistic picture of our research work; the physical environment being used for this research work is depicted in the figure 1. Core network's (MPLS Backbone) position in the circle comprises of different Cisco Based routers connected with two different networks mentioned as *Ring1* and *Ring2*. Each Ring network comprises of routers which are connected to the users of the organization via switches. Among these users, the user X (the authors) is the key user who is managing the whole activity. Thus, user X, running on a windows 7 based machine, is used as a network analyzer to capture traffic across the domains.

The arrangement shown in figure 1 is first configured for MPLS VPN in real time to generate traffic where users are connected to the network as usual. Then we introduced attacks (DOS, DDOS, and TCP) onto the network and the data produced is captured through a Network Analyzer whireshark¹ at different intervals of time.

Similarly, the paper also includes the study of VPN over Frame Relay on the same pattern described above. Two sites *Ring 1* ,*Ring 2* are connected over frame relay. Ring 1 includes users who are trying to access different data server across the link on the other side.. After configuring the links and establishing the circuits we configured VPN over frame relay link and capture the traffic when different attacks -- DoS, DDoS & TCP are generated. We captured Data and analyze the behavior of VPN over Frame Relay before the attacks and after the attacks(Generated by User X).

Fig 1: Environment Design

IV. ANALYSIS

For our research work we have implement a real environment dissuaded in design section and test the results in that environment. We have implement both MPLS based VPN and Frame Relay based VPN in the environment. During communication over both the domain we create different attacks to see the impact of both side against that attacks, We take data at random interval of time to check the proper result &/or behavior of both side against those attacks in figure 2. We have use DoS, DDoS attacks in this research work with TCP half window session. In MPLS based VPN the data rate shown was very high with proper IP usage of the link, the result show that in MPLS based VPN when there was no attacks generated the maximum inbound data rate was 80 mega bits/sec, minimum inbound data rate was 60 mega bits/sec. In the same environment the maximum outbound data rate was 135MB/sec, minimum outbound data rate 100 Mb/sec.

Similarly In Frame Relay based VPN, before attack - the maximum inbound data rate was 70 Mb/sec, minimum inbound data rate was 60 Mb/sec. In the same environment the maximum outbound data rate was 155 Mb/sec, minimum outbound data rate 100 Mb/sec.

¹ Wireshark is free and open source packet analyzer available at <http://wireshark.en.softonic.com/>

Fig 2: MPLS VPN, Frame Relay VPN without Attacks

If we compare the behavior of MPLS before and after attacks, we see a stable behavior of MPLS VPN as compared to Frame Relay VPN as shown in figure 3. When DoS, DDoS attacks are generated it results in full CAM memory so legal user will not be able to access the network or data. The TCP half window size keep many sessions open so no user will be able to login to your network. The graph which show zero inbound and outbound traffic of Frame Relay VPN. While MPLS VPN in attacks shows stable behavior as minimum inbound data rate was 20Mb/sec and maximum 25Mb/sec while the minimum outbound data rate was 30Mb/sec and maximum outbound data rate was 35 Mb/sec. The results shows that when attacks are generated in Frame relay based VPN environment it effect up to large extent and the because of attacks on the environment users are not able to access the network or data while MPLS VPN resist against attacks and show stability in its behavior.

Fig 3: MPLS VPN ,Frame Relay VPN with Attacks

V. CONCLUSION

Security is major concern of all the networks in today's era. As technology is evolved and gives more benefits to the users so at the same time it creates a lot of black hole for the users. Virtual Private Network (VPN) is used to interconnect different offices in a secure manner with right WAN technology to be used. This research work is based on the concept that which technology i.e. MPLS or Frame Relay based VPN are more secure against DoS, DDoS and TCP attacks. We have configure both of technology in a real environment and keeping in view different aspect, data nature, communication pattern, at different interval of time, we monitor the behavior of each technology in a normal communication phase and when we generate different attacks on both technology then again the behavior was noted down so to analyze that what is the effect of attacks on the behavior of both side.

We found same behavior of MPLS based VPN before attacks and after attacks. Thus, during communication a user will not see resources not available as this protocol handle the attacks in a proper manner which is show by the communication channel. While Frame Relay based VPN shows a big variation i.e. before generating attacks the communication was normal with a low data rate then MPLS, but when attacks were generated so we found that a user was not able then to access any resources across the network. A complete data loss and zero inbound data rate was noticed.

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